

Comparative study: BF Paradac and Primol

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Abstract

The interrelationships between friability between dissolution, moisture, disintegration and hardness in compressed BF Paradac tab 500 mg and Promol tab 500 mg were studied by compressing tablets prepared from granulation processes of extrusion, molding or Lyophilisation

(freeze-drying) containing low level of moisture. The change in hardness, disintegration and dissolution of the tablets were observed upon being exposed to room conditions. An equilibration was conducted under high humidities are expected to result in a decrease in the hardness of the tablets linearly depending on the tablets' hardness at compression time. The softened tablets are tested and expected to increase hardness after being exposed to an ambient room conditions overnight. The increase in hardness magnitude depends on the hardness of the tablets after compression time. Increasing the hardness of the tablets is expected to result in an increase in disintegration time. The drugs are also subjected to a vitro dissolution and effects are observed. The expected results imply that gaining moisture and resultant storage loss in a different humidity conditions explain the major hardness increases of the compressed tablets in storage.

Introduction

The use of substandard medication is harmful to the health of people and the sale of the drugs has more far reaching effects on the health of families and populations. Patients and the society are more likely to lose faith in healthcare establishments and professionals including the pharmacists and physicians are they are subjected to the use of substandard medications. It is therefore important to regulate the entry and sale of any medicine and must go through quality standards for acceptance (Rieker and Rand, 2002). Quality tests must be conducted to ensure safety and therapeutic activity of the formulations and their performance must be consistent and predictable. Pharmaceutical products are evaluated for their physiochemical properties to ensure their quality and bioavailability as well as the ability to impart optimum therapeutic activity (Avis, 2018). BF Paradac and Promol were chosen for the comparative study as they are widely used worldwide for the treatment of moderate and severe fever and pain. The characteristics as well as side effects and misuse are highlighted in this study.

Promol 500mg and BF Paradac tablets swallowed, chewed, dissolved or dispersed in water before administration. The particles contain one or more substances with or without such as glidants, binders, diluents, disintegrating agents, lubricants and substances that can modify the preparation mode of the digestive tract. BF-Paradac is a tablet with acetaminophen 500mg as the active ingredient. It is used as a temporary relief for minor aches and pains linked to common colds, muscle ache, headache, and toothache and fever reduction. Due to the presence of acetaminophen, it poses risk of severe liver damage if more than six tablets are which is the maximum amount for daily intake. The risk can also be aggravated if the drug is taken with other drugs that contain acetaminophen or when taking at least three alcoholic drinks daily when sing the drug. Using acetaminophen can also cause severe skin reactions characterized by such symptoms as skin reddening, rashes, and blisters and use should be stopped upon the occurrence of these symptoms and further medical help sought. The drug should not be used with any pother drug that contains acetaminophen for more than ten days for pain and 3 days for fever. The inactive ingredients in the drug include corn starch, stearic acid, sodium starch glycolate, ethylparabean, povidone and pregelatinized starch. The drug s stored at room temperature tightly closed.

The Promol tablet is used in the relief of mild and moderate pain like headache, cold flu, tooth ache, period pains and joint pains. It works to reduce the activity of certain chemicals in the body to relieve it of pain. It is used in fever relief by increasing body heat loss. The drug can be used with other drugs such as aspirin, and Caffeine for migraine pain relief. Promol is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug used in pain decrease and prevention of blood clotting and

reduction of inflammation when in higher doses. Overdose of Promol causes abdominal pain, pancreatic inflammation, kidney injury, appetite loss, pale skin color, vomiting, increased body acids, and liver failure. The side effects associated with using Promol include bleeding, skin rashes, mouth ulcers, breathing problems, swellings of face, lips, throat and tongue, allergic reactions, blood disorders, rashes and swelling as mild ones and skin reactions such as skin reddening, blisters and skin rashes in severe cases. (Bulajeva et al, 2014) It can also cause liver damage and possible death. Three f more daily alcohol drinks a day can increase risk for liver damage when using the drug. The drug should not be use with other dugs containing Promol as this increases the level of the drug in the body and can therefore increase the risk for liver damage and stomach bleeding. Promol can interact with anticoagulants such as warfarin and coumarins used for clotting prevention. The drug can also interact with Prokinetic agents such as metoclopramide used for symptom relief in diabetic patients. It can also react with antiemetic drugs such as domperidone based in the treatment of vomiting and nausea (Lee et al, 2013). Promol also interacts with antihyperlipidemic agents such as cholestyramine used in lowering the levels of cholesterol. Promol reacts with antineoplastic agents such as imatinib used in leukemia treatment. Ibufen, and Paracetamol contain Promol can should be combined.

The two drugs, BR Paradac and Promol are pain relieving medicines with similar characteristics and side effects. This report analyses the preparation standards observed when producing the two drugs.

Materials and Methodology

The industrial manufacture of oral dosage requires such quality tests as hardness, dissolution, friability, disintegration, and moisture content also known as loss of drying.

The disintegration test by the European Pharmacopoeia uses 200ml of water at 15-25 Celsius degrees and gas bubbles to simulate the oral environment and estimating of water absorption ratio.

The friability test was conducted to test the physical strength of the tablets, the tendency of the tablets to break into smaller pieces under duress of contact and supplement other measurements such as the breaking force of the tablets of the tablets was tested using a friability tester balled Copley FR2000 and the rotation rates and friability results were recorded. The test was aimed at determining if the formulations pass or fail their BP specification.

Hardness was tested to determine the resistance of tablet crushing as measured by the amount of force necessary for disrupting them and crushing. Hardness test intended to test the resistance of tablets to crushing was measured by a calibrated Erweka Tablet tester that measures the diameter, thickness and hardness. The tester is made of two jaws facing each other simulating the human jaws.

Disintegration of the tablets was tested to determine if the tablets would disintegrate within a specified duration of time when placed in a liquid medium of experimental conditions (Lippincott, Wiliams and Watson, 2005). Tablet disintegration must be ensured in a specific time period as small differences during high compression leads to the production of tablets with varying break up abilities. Disintegration was tested using the Pharmag Pharma test disc 3

disintegration tester under a water bath of temperature of 37 degrees. The integration time was recorded for samples of each tablet.

Dissolution was tested in a simulated gastric environment to test dissolution problems. The test is done for dissolution compliance requirements determination for solid dosage that is orally administered. This was done using the Basket stirring apparatus.

Moisture content determination or loss on drying was conducted to determine the volatile matter amount in the tablets driven ff under specific conditions. The tablets were crushed and a sample put into a bottle and weight records taken. The bottle and its contents were shaken and placed in an oven and allowed to cool. Weight loss was then observed and recorded.

Results

Friability test

The purpose of friability test was to verify if the tablets could withstand wear and tear during transportation. The friability test was aimed at reflecting hardness of the tablet (Sinko, 2005). The tablets were subjected to Copley FR2000 friability tester. Tablets were selected and their W1 initial weights recorded, after which they were subjected to the Friability tester. The friability tester was operated for four minutes at the speed of 25 rotations per minute and 100 revolutions. The weights of the tablets were taken W2 and the percentage weight loss, the friability, was calculated with the formula $\text{Friability}\% = (W1 - W2) \times 100$. The officially permissible friability minute is 1% (Krousel-Wood, Thomas, Muntner and Morisky, 2004).

BF Paradac lost -0.45595% representing a mass of 0.0313g loss. Promol lost a mass of 0.0262 making up 0.37237% of the total weight. A maximum weight loss of not more than 1% of the total weight loss after friability test using friability test results is considered generally acceptable and the broken or smashed tablets will not be salvaged. In the present study, the tablets of the two drugs showed friability of below one friability percentage. The minimal friability values registered by samples of the two drugs indicate that they have the ability to withstand stress due to abrasive forces (Mims, Turcker, Calson, Scheneider and Bagdy, 2009). The fact that the tablets cannot crumble during transportation, dispensing and handling means that the two brands have highly satisfactory evaluation characteristics as indicated by the friability specifications and valued of less than one per cent (Morisky, 2008).

Disintegration test was conducted by breaking the tables of the two drugs into small granules as a prior test for dissolution which is, in turn, part of the in-vitro- in vivo correlation that allows the tablets to be broken into smaller articles able to pass through the size 10 mesh of the Bracket rack apparatus of the Pharmag Pharma Test Disk 3 Disintegration tester (Ferner e al.,2001). The temperature was set at 37 degrees Celsius with a maximum time of 50 minutes of required time. The tester was motor operated and driven at 30 revolutions per minute. Time was noted for the when all the particles from all the tubes had passed through the tube mesh. The process was repeated for the two brands of drugs. The average passing time was noted the process repeated for all the two medicine brands. The disintegration test results showed that the tested drug brands registered a disintegration time of less than 6 minutes which was less than the 15 minute disintegration time for uncoated tablets. This proves that the drugs passed the quality control limits as per the pharmacopoeia. The disintegration time registered by the two drug

brands proves that they disintegrate fast for absorption meaning that the onset of the time will be reduced.

Dissolution test the dissolution test was meant to simulate the gastric environment and the bioavailability of the drugs (Ferner and Aronson, 2000). The test aimed to confirm the release pattern of the drug dosage from and its efficacy. The test is also part of the in-vitro in-vivo correlation meaning that all the tests parameters were set as per the in-vivo human body conditions. The dissolution test was performed using the Dissolution tester. To determine the release of the drugs, 900ml of phosphate buffer, a pH of 5.4 was set the medium for dissolution. Time was set at intervals of 5, 10, 15, 30, 45 and 60 minutes as the sampling time. The medium for dissolution was heated to 37 degrees centigrade and using an auto heater. The tablet samples were stirred immediately at the 50 rotations per minute. A sample of the drug solution was withdrawn, diluted with fresh solvent and the drug amounts was determined. The dissolution result tests showed that the two drug brands release about 10% within an hour. This means that the drug on the onset of action will be fast. This means that the two drugs complied with the standards of pharmacopoeia.

Hardness test is performed to ensure determine damage resistance during handling, packaging, and transportation (Aulton, 2006). For the drugs to withstand the mechanical shocks that occur during manufacture, packaging and transport, the tablet needs an amount of hardness (Cina, Fanikos, Mitton, McCrea and Churchill, 2006). The tablets should also be able to withstand reasonable user abuse when in their hands. The hardness is also important for acceptance (Williams, Amico, Bova and Womack, 2013). The tablets position during the measurement process is important and must be that which is readily and easily reproduced by operators. The hardness tester automatically did the position orientation of the drugs. One of the unforeseen findings of the tests was that the two drugs showed standard deviation within the acceptable range. The two drug brands showed comparatively acceptable standard deviation of their hardness (Walker, 2014).

Conclusion

The two drug brands in the study complied with the set specifications for friability, hardness, dissolution and disintegration (Liu, Wu and Chen, 2010). The minimal variations in standard deviation of hardness showed that further studies are needed for potency and dissolution profiles of the drugs for confirmation of their pharmaceutical equivalence. The tablets assessed in this exercise were subjected to test on different quality parameters of weights, diameter, friability, thickness, disintegration, dissolution, hardness and assay using compendia methods before they are released into the market after production (Florence and Attwood, 2006). The study proved that the drugs passed the friability, dissolution, hardness and disintegration tests in accordance with the British pharmacopoeia. The dissolution test showed that the two drug brands were within the set limit by the pharmacopoeia (Betrgkvist et al.,2009). Generally, the results of the study in the quality investigation of the two drug brands showed that they passed the minimums set by the quality evaluation criteria set for entry into legal markers and are, therefore, source of medication. This implies that legal vendors with the drugs are not counterfeiting, probably due t the fact that they are cheaper than other medicines and are, therefore, available over the counter (Washington, 2000). There are many quality control authorities in every country in the world with their quality evaluation criteria and standards for medication sold in their markets. These authorities work with law enforcement formations to counter the sale and

distribution of illegal and substandard medicines (Basco, 2004). Drug effectiveness is directly related to the quality ensured by the quality evaluations of medication in the process of production and distribution. Counterfeit drugs do not meet the quality standards set by regulatory and quality control authorities.

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